

Calculations of Great Interest Suggest a Consistent Story as a Promising Candidate for the Super Unified Theory of Physics

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Abstract

As an invitation to another paper introducing a comprehensive theory that can address a great number of conundrums from particle physics to cosmology, in this short paper, I will pick up several astonishing calculations which can hardly be dismissed as coincidences, indicating that the underlying theory is too beautiful to be wrong.

The electromagnetic force between electrons is stronger than the gravitation between them by a factor of $k_0 e^2 / G m_e^2 = 4.16 \times 10^{42}$. Denote $M = 2.04 \times 10^{21}$ as the square root of the hierarchy gap.

The mass of electron can be calculated as

$$m_e = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2} \frac{1}{4M} \sqrt{\frac{c\hbar}{8G}}$$

In addition to the well-known fact that the mass of proton is

$$m_p = 6\pi^5 m_e$$

the theoretical mass of up, down and strange quark can be expressed in multiples of electron mass as

$$m_u = 2\pi^{\frac{2}{3}} m_e$$

$$m_d = 2\pi^{\frac{4}{3}} m_e$$

$$m_s = 6\pi^3 m_e = m_p / \pi^2$$

respectively.

All these facts can be derived from the equation presented in below

$$\frac{k_0 e^2}{\left(\hbar / \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2} \frac{4mc}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2}}\right)^2} = \frac{Gm^2}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{2G\hbar}{c^3}}\right)^2}$$
$$\Leftrightarrow k_0 \left(\frac{e}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2}}\right)^2 = \frac{\hbar c}{128}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow k_0 \left(\frac{8e}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2}} \right)^2 = \frac{\hbar c}{2}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0}} \left(\frac{8e}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2}} \right)^2 = \frac{h}{\sqrt{\mu_0}}$$

The mean lifetime of free neutron measured by the beam method can be calculated as

$$T_{beam} = \frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{2G\hbar}{c^3}} 6\pi^5 \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2} M^2/c$$

which can be linked with the lifetime measured by bottle method via Lorentz factor of $c/8$.

$$T_{beam} = \frac{T_{bottle}}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{8}\right)^2}}$$

Denote the adjusted mass of proton by Lorentz factor of $c/4$ as

$$\dot{m} = \frac{m_p}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2}} \approx 969 [MeV / c^2]$$

the mass of baryons composed of u/d/s quarks (except proton and neutron) align in a periodic table as shown in below.

Denote the latest observed figure of baryonic density in our universe as $\rho_B = 4.25 \times 10^{-28} [kg / m^3]$, let $\rho = 8\rho_B$, and $N = 9.41 \times 10^{39}$ (as the square root of the Eddington number), then

$$\frac{2c}{\sqrt{\frac{8\pi G\rho}{3}}} = N$$

$$\frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{c}{\sqrt{\frac{8\pi G\rho}{3}}} \right)^3 \rho}{m_p} = N^2$$

M and N have a relationship that

$$N = \frac{2}{3\pi^5 \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2}} M^2 \approx \frac{M^2}{444}$$

Take

$$M_0 N_0 = 1 \rightarrow \frac{M_0^3}{444} \approx 1$$

$$M_0 \approx 7.63 \quad N_0 \approx 1.31 \times 10^{-1}$$

as the initial condition, we may find with surprise that

$$\frac{2c}{\sqrt{\frac{8\pi G\rho}{3}}} \times \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^3 = \sqrt{\frac{2G\hbar}{c^3}}$$

For the detailed meaning of all those calculations and the underlying theory, please refer to my thesis titled "Spontaneous breaking of spatial symmetry provides a novel paradigm for theoretical physics".